

A NOVEL ADAPTIVE HYSTERESIS CONSTANT FREQUENCY CURRENT CONTROL

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Abstract

This paper presents a novel adaptive-hysteresis predetermined constant frequency current-mode control for PWM DC/DC power converters. Theoretical examination is performed and one simple and easy-to-apply control law is derived. It is concluded that very fast and accurate response is maintained, while predetermined constant frequency steady-state operation is achieved. Moreover, the control law attains very small frequency variations during transients. Experimental 2KW buck converter is built to verify the theory. Some steady-state and transient tests are performed with results, which are consistent with the theory.

1. Introduction

Ever since the current-mode control has been accepted as a conventional method to control PWM DC/DC converters, much of the investigation work was involved in developing the best possible way to achieve perfect regulation. The perfect regulation requires constant switching frequency, linear steady-state transfer ratio and theoretically indefinitely high bandwidth. Three methods are currently in use: hysteretic regulation, peak current-mode and average current-mode. All of them show significant deviations from the perfect case.

The hysteretic regulation [1], as commonly used, features linear transfer ratio and extremely fast and accurate response. However, the switching frequency is not constant, which makes the filtering and thermal issues very difficult.

The peak current-mode [2,3] operates with constant switching frequency, but inherent instability with duty-cycle beyond 50% calls for compensation ramp. Finally, neither linear transfer nor high bandwidth is achieved.

The average current-mode [4,5] features linear transfer ratio and constant switching frequency, but the bandwidth is rather low if good stability margin is required.

Another method for current programming was presented in [6]. It has very good characteristics: constant switching frequency and good dynamic features. The main disadvantage is that it is very sensitive to inductance variations. This can be a serious drawback in high-current devices where inductance significantly changes with current level.

As shown in this section, the topic remains unfinished. The suitable operating method that is very close to the perfect case was not developed yet. One possible solution is presented in this paper, which

appears as a combination of the previously mentioned techniques. Such a combination produces control algorithm, which assures all hysteretic-like features but with predetermined constant frequency, even in transients.

The paper is organized as follows: section 2 presents the background of the method. Some design guidelines are shown in section 3. Verification of the method is given by experimental results in section 4. The conclusion from the investigations are made and proposed in section 5.

2. Theoretical background

Of all aforementioned methods, the hysteretic regulation offers more advantages than the others do. The switching frequency variations can be reduced or even cancelled by properly chosen hysteretic window H . Therefore, the focus of the paper will be the improvement of hysteresis window generation. Since the steady-state constant frequency operation is a demanding request, it is necessary to examine the steady-state waveforms. The inductor current steady-state waveform is shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1: The steady-state inductor current waveform

The hysteretic type of operation is based on limiting the inductor current excursion from the reference value. H_1 is the level of excursion during the switch-on interval, and H_2 is the level of excursion during the switch-off interval. In general, $H_1 \neq H_2$. Of course, it is commonly implemented that $H_1 = H_2$. This assures that average inductor current equals the reference value I_{ref} . From Fig.1, it is easily derived that:

$$H_1 = H_2 = H^* = \frac{V_{off} t_{off}}{2L} = \frac{V_{off} T}{2L} (1 - D) \quad (1)$$

where:

H^* is a hysteresis window in steady-state,

t_{off} is the switch-off period,

V_{off} is the inductor voltage during t_{off} ,

L is the inductance value,

D is the steady-state duty-cycle value.

T is the switching period.

A closer look at (1) reveals that H^* is independent on average inductor current. This implies that as long as the inductor current is continuous (converter in CCM mode), the same control law can be used to keep the switching frequency constant. Furthermore, if we want the constant switching period T , we

must have the hysteretic window H that satisfies (1). Therefore, this value must be calculated on-line and it evolves into adaptive-hysteresis constant-frequency current control.

On-line calculation is made by using the equivalent expression:

$$H(t) = \frac{V_{off} T}{2L} - \frac{1}{T} \int_0^t \frac{V_{off} T}{2L} dt, \quad (2)$$

which, in steady-state, gives (1). An assumption that V_{off} is ripple-free has been made, which is based on a fact that output voltage ripple is much smaller than the inductor current ripple in well-designed converters. In such a way, the hysteresis window ripple is negligible and it will not disturb the current regulation.

For now, it is discovered how to keep the constant frequency. Another issue is how to program it, i.e. how to assure that the frequency is equal to some predetermined value. The answer will be given in the next section.

3. Design guidelines

In mid- and high-power devices, it is highly recommended the use of inductor current sensor. This is due to the early detection of inductor current saturation. If the deep saturation occurs, it can cause serious hazards in the circuit. Therefore, the presented method is very suitable for this type of devices.

The eq.(2) can be realized in analog way using the block-diagram shown in Fig.2. It is clear that V_{off} is generated from the circuit voltages using coefficients K_1 and K_2 , which are equal to 0 or ± 1 depending on the converter topology. Then, it is scaled by $T/2L$ value, and it is integrated from the beginning of the cycle. The upper (H_1) and the lower (H_2) current limit are generated in usual way and they form the band within which the inductor current signal is located. As the current signal reaches the upper bound, the switch turns off and the integrator is disabled ($R=0, EN=0$) thus keeping the constant width of the current band until the next cycle. When the current reaches the lower bound, the switch turns on, the new cycle is started and the integrator is reset and enabled ($R=unit\ impulse, EN=1$).

Fig.2: The control circuit block-diagram

As an illustration, the simulated control circuit waveforms are presented in Fig.3. The inductor current is shown using thick line. The upper and the lower bounds are forming a band that limits the current excursion. The points when the switch is turned on can be easily recognized by sudden change in boundary values. When the switch turns off, the bound remains constant till the end of the cycle.

If the inductor current sensor has the transfer ratio other than unity, than the value of R_s must be included in the calculation simply by substitution of $T/2L$ with $R_s T/2L$ and I_{ref} with $R_s I_{ref}$.

Fig.3: The control circuit waveforms

Achieving the predetermined constant switching frequency is straightforward: for known inductance value L , inductor current sensor transfer ratio R_s and required switching period T , the factor $R_s T/2L$ is calculated. Then, after the V_{off} is formed, it should be scaled down by exactly the same factor as it was calculated in the previous step. In such a way, the operating frequency should be equal to the referenced value.

4. Experiment

In order to verify the analysis, the experimental buck converter is built with following parameters: $L=6\text{mH}$, $C=100\mu\text{F}$, $R=24\Omega$, $V_{in}\in(200\text{V}, 300\text{V})$ with nominal load current of 10A. The inductor current sensor was a hall-type closed-loop isolated sensor with overall transfer ratio of $R_s=0.5\Omega$.

The switching frequency is chosen to be approximately 3kHz, which can be met in high-voltage mid-power devices. Now, all the necessary data is given and the control circuit can be designed. The control circuit was made completely analog, using general-purpose components for commercial temperature range. None of the offsets was compensated, so some deviations from the perfect case can be expected.

4.1 Steady-state examination

The first experiment of interest was to examine the steady state waveforms. Fig.4 shows the control circuit waveforms, as already explained in section 3. Thick line represents the sensed inductor current signal. The waveforms agree very close to the theory, so the final result is the tight control of the inductor current. The upper and the lower bound follow the eq.(2), thus forming the band that is symmetrical to the reference current value. Therefore, the inductor current is equal to the reference.

Another issue of interest was the switching frequency variations for different operating conditions. The load was the same (resistive load of 24Ω), but the reference current and the input voltage were changed in order to achieve full range of steady-state operating conditions. Fig.5 shows the steady-state switching frequency variations. It is clear that the frequency varies for a small amount, due to the imperfections of the control circuit. Namely, eq.(2) and Fig.2 require perfect matching of switching period T in scaling factor $T/2L$ and resettable integrator time constant. Due to a small error, the switching frequency would not be ideally invariable. Some fine-tuning could cancel the variations. However, the change in frequency is small enough to be practically neglected.

Fig.4: Experimental control circuit waveforms in steady-state

Fig.5: Switching frequency variations for different operating conditions

4.2 Transient state examination

Although the constant frequency steady-state operation is satisfactory, further improvement would be to have (nearly) constant frequency in transient state. So, to see whether it is possible, the reference inductor current was suddenly changed from app. 5A to app. 7A (a change of 40%). Fig.6 shows the inductor current response together with its reference value. In order to find the switching frequency variations, the period T of each cycle is determined and shown in Fig.6 below the waveforms. Three conclusions can be made:

- the current response is extremely fast, as expected for the hysteretic regulation,
- the current ripple within one cycle is symmetrical to the reference value, as already seen in Fig.4,
- the frequency changes for a small amount during beginning of the transient, but as soon as inductor current reaches the reference value, the switching period T is coming to its old steady-state value.

Fig.6: The inductor current and its reference value waveforms in transient state

Of course, the transient is not finished due to the change in output voltage. The entire transient is shown in Fig.7. The current loop makes the average inductor current equal to the reference value after 3-4 switching periods and keep it that way through the rest of the transient which lasts much longer. Therefore, the output RC circuit behind the inductor acts as it was charged by the constant current source (which is practically true).

Fig.7: The inductor current (lower trace) and output voltage (upper trace) transient waveforms

Finally, an unusual test for the buck circuit was performed: the inductor current reference value was consisting of the DC value and a significant AC component with the 300Hz frequency (one tenth of the switching frequency). This test actually investigates the possibility of the current loop to be employed in DC/AC power inverters or PFC DC/AC converters. Fig.8 shows the inductor current response.

At first glance, it can be concluded that there are ten switching periods in one AC-component period, which proves the 3kHz switching frequency. Additionally, the reference value contains more that 100% peak-to-peak ripple, but the inductor current seems to track the reference value quite satisfactorily. This gives rise to an idea of successful implementation of this current control method in regulation of AC component.

Fig.8: The inductor current tracking the reference value with high AC component.

5. Conclusion

In this paper a new adaptive hysteresis current control method is presented which offers constant frequency at steady-state operation and nearly constant frequency at transient operation. The method is based on knowledge of the converter principle of operation and it is quite simple to implement. Theoretical background is presented, resulting in one simple control law, which can be realized using standard analog circuits. The method is applicable to all types of DC/DC converters.

The steady-state operation is investigated, and it is concluded that the switching frequency is constant and equal to the predetermined value. Moreover, in transient states, the frequency slightly changes until the inductor average current comes close to the new reference value and then the frequency restores to the original level. Since the operating frequency is a parameter in hysteretic regulation, its controllability is very good.

Additionally, the ability of the current loop to regulate the AC component was examined. It is concluded that the AC component of the frequency as high as one tenth of the switching frequency can be successfully regulated. Therefore, the method is a good candidate for the current-control in high-power PFC applications and DC/AC inverters.

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